

OHOS: The Podcast! Episode 1: The Covid Art Archive with Glasgow Disability Alliance

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OHOS has a podcast! With jokes and transitions and everything. This is our first episode, with another on the way. Do give it a listen.

With thanks to Lewis and Hannah from the Glasgow Disability Alliance (GDA) for their guidance and brilliance, and Paul from GDA for his emcee wizardry. Thanks also goes, of course, to all of the marvellous participants featured in the episode, and to our delightful editor John McDiarmid at [Telt Media](#).

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